

VI. THE COLLATZ CONJETURE

Order and harmony in the sequence numbers

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All the sequences formed with the Collatz function always reach number 16 and it is after 4 more iterations that they reach number 1. Why do all the sequences reach number 16? This number can result from the number 32 or the number 5. They are both numbers of the form $9n + 5$ and both have the same digital root $dr(5)$. The number 16 is of the form $9n + 7$ and its digital root is $dr(7)$.

In the following table, the numbers classified in rows, according to the value of their digital root (column 0).

n	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	...
$9n+8$	8	17	26	35	44	53	62	71	80	89	98	107	116	125	134	143	152	161	170	179	188	197	206	215	224	233	242	251	260	269	278	287	296	305	314	323	332	341	350	359	...
$9n+6$	6	15	24	33	42	51	60	69	78	87	96	105	114	123	132	141	150	159	168	177	186	195	204	213	222	231	240	249	258	267	276	285	294	303	312	321	330	339	348	357	...
$9n+4$	4	13	22	31	40	49	58	67	76	85	94	103	112	121	130	139	148	157	166	175	184	193	202	211	220	229	238	247	256	265	274	283	292	301	310	319	328	337	346	355	...
$9n+2$	2	11	20	29	38	47	56	65	74	83	92	101	110	119	128	137	146	155	164	173	182	191	200	209	218	227	236	245	254	263	272	281	290	299	308	317	326	335	344	353	...
$9n+1$	1	10	19	28	37	46	55	64	73	82	91	100	109	118	127	136	145	154	163	172	181	190	199	208	217	226	235	244	253	262	271	280	289	298	307	316	325	334	343	352	...
$9n+3$	3	12	21	30	39	48	57	66	75	84	93	102	111	120	129	138	147	156	165	174	183	192	201	210	219	228	237	246	255	264	273	282	291	300	309	318	327	336	345	354	...
$9n+5$	5	14	23	32	41	50	59	68	77	86	95	104	113	122	131	140	149	158	167	176	185	194	203	212	221	230	239	248	257	266	275	284	293	302	311	320	329	338	347	356	...
$9n+7$	7	16	25	34	43	52	61	70	79	88	97	106	115	124	133	142	151	160	169	178	187	196	205	214	223	232	241	250	259	268	277	286	295	304	313	322	331	340	349	358	...
$9n+9$	9	18	27	36	45	54	63	72	81	90	99	108	117	126	135	144	153	162	171	180	189	198	207	216	225	234	243	252	261	270	279	288	297	306	315	324	333	342	351	360	...

In the following table, the even numbers, classified in the same way.

Números pares con raíz digital 7	$2(9n+8)$	16	34	52	70	88	106	124	142	160	178	196	214	232	250	268	286	304	322	340	358	...
Números pares con raíz digital 3	$2(9n+6)$	12	30	48	66	84	102	120	138	156	174	192	210	228	246	264	282	300	318	336	354	...
Números pares con raíz digital 8	$2(9n+4)$	8	26	44	62	80	98	116	134	152	170	188	206	224	242	260	278	296	314	332	350	...
Números pares con raíz digital 4	$2(9n+2)$	4	22	40	58	76	94	112	130	148	166	184	202	220	238	256	274	292	310	328	346	...
Números pares con raíz digital 2	$2(9n+1)$	2	20	38	56	74	92	110	128	146	164	182	200	218	236	254	272	290	308	326	344	...
Números pares con raíz digital 6	$2(9n+3)$	6	24	42	60	78	96	114	132	150	168	186	204	222	240	258	276	294	312	330	348	...
Números pares con raíz digital 1	$2(9n+5)$	10	28	46	64	82	100	118	136	154	172	190	208	226	244	262	280	298	316	334	352	...
Números pares con raíz digital 5	$2(9n+7)$	14	32	50	68	86	104	122	140	158	176	194	212	230	248	266	284	302	320	338	356	...
Números pares con raíz digital 9	$2(9n+9)$	18	36	54	72	90	108	126	144	162	180	198	216	234	252	270	288	306	324	342	360	...

Even numbers of the form $9n + 8$, $dr(8)$ reach the numbers of the form $9n + 4$, $dr(4)$
 Even numbers of the form $9n + 3$, $dr(3)$ reach the numbers of the form $9n + 6$, $dr(6)$
 Even numbers of the form $9n + 4$, $dr(4)$ reach the numbers of the form $9n + 2$, $dr(2)$
 Even numbers of the form $9n + 2$, $dr(2)$ reach the numbers of the form $9n + 1$, $dr(1)$
 Even numbers of the form $9n + 6$, $dr(6)$ reach the numbers of the form $9n + 3$, $dr(3)$
 Even numbers of the form $9n + 1$, $dr(1)$ reach the numbers of the form $9n + 5$, $dr(5)$
 Even numbers of the form $9n + 5$, $dr(5)$ reach the numbers of the form $9n + 7$, $dr(7)$
 Even numbers of the form $9n + 7$, $dr(7)$ reach the numbers of the form $9n + 8$, $dr(8)$
 Even numbers of the form $9n + 9$, $dr(9)$ reach the numbers of the form $9n + 9$, $dr(9)$

Odd numbers of the form $9n + 8$, $dr(8)$ reach the numbers of the form $9n + 7$, $dr(7)$
 Odd numbers of the form $9n + 4$, $dr(4)$ reach the numbers of the form $9n + 4$, $dr(4)$
 Etc, etc, etc.

From now on and to simplify the text, the numbers form will be replaced by the value of their digital root $dr(n)$.

The following graph represents the transformation of the numbers in each iteration, according to the value of their digital root. Arrows indicate the direction of the iterations.

(par5) in blue color, which represents all the even numbers with digital root $dr(5)$, is the first value of the graph, but it could be any other, because the numbers are transformed by iterating in a closed loop in which the last numbers start a new cycle. For example, the value (par1), in the last cycle of the graph, becomes (impar5), but also (par5), going back to the beginning.

It is essential to observe in the graph that the transformations of the odd numbers in the first iteration are to even numbers $dr(4)$ and $dr(7)$ and in the next iteration the $dr(4)$ are also $dr(7)$. If those even numbers, $dr(4)$ and $dr(7)$, iterate to an even number, the result is even numbers $dr(2)$ and $dr(8)$ and in the next iteration the $dr(8)$ are also $dr(2)$ and those numbers iterate until an even number $dr(7)$ results.

A singularity of even numbers with digital root $dr(7)$ is that they are the only numbers with a single possibility to iterate and they do so to an even number $dr(8)$, since when they iterate to an odd number $dr(8)$, it iterates back to an even number $dr(7)$. On the other hand, the iteration of an even number $dr(8)$ is to an even number $dr(4)$, since when they iterate to an odd number $dr(4)$, it iterates again to an even number $dr(4)$.

The Collatz function causes all the numbers, even and odd, in their iterations to become even numbers with digital root $dr(7)$ and they iterate to another even number with digital root $dr(8)$ and these to an even number with digital root $dr(4)$. At this point the sequence can return to an even number $dr(7)$ if $dr(4)$ iterates to an odd number $dr(2)$ or reach an odd number $dr(1)$ if it iterates to an even number $dr(2)$.

The answer to the question at the beginning of this paper is that all the sequences of the Collatz function arrive at the number 16 because all the numbers are transformed into an even number with digital root $dr(7)$ and the smallest of those numbers is 16.

The following graph represents the three cycles in which the numbers move, according to their digital root, when applying the Collatz function.

The even numbers $dr(3)$ and $dr(6)$ form a closed loop in which they iterate from each other or to odd numbers $dr(3)$ and $dr(6)$, which become even numbers $dr(1)$ and enter the general cycle.

The even numbers $dr(9)$ iterate alone to another even number $dr(9)$ or to an odd number $dr(9)$, transforming into an even number $dr(1)$ and entering the general cycle.

In the center of the graph the general cycle is represented where the odd and even numbers $dr(1)$, $dr(5)$, $dr(7)$, $dr(8)$, $dr(4)$ and $dr(2)$ iterate.

All iterations of a Collatz sequence occur in a closed loop with no end, following the pattern of the graph. Closed loop without end because the sequence does not end when it reaches number 1, but iterates indefinitely at 4, 2, 1, 4, 2, 1, . . . The infinity of this loop can be seen in the graph, which also shows the impossibility of a sequence with a period other than 4, 2, 1.

